

D5.1 Intermediate Impact Report v1.0

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Programa de Universalización de
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Dissemination Level

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PP	Restricted to other program participants
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium
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Tipo

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RE	Report
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Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5th Generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
OpenCAPIF	Open Common API Framework
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MCU	Microcontroller Unit
Open-Verso	Open, Virtualized Technology Demonstrators for Smart Networks
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
QoS	Quality of Service
SDG	Software Development Groups
TARGET-X	Trial Platform for 5G Evolution – Cross-Industry On Large Scale
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
V2X	Vehicle to everything

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable "D5.1 – Intermediate Impact Report" of the 6GTWINROAD-MNO subproject, "AI/ML driven 6G public networks enabling future V2X services". This document reports the related results with the generation of impact carried out during the first part of the project by i2CAT. Being part of a common project, 6GTWINROAD, some of the activities carried out are common to all subprojects.

In particular, this deliverable reports activities related to communication, dissemination and standardization, as well as impact indicators and reporting and monitoring mechanisms.

1 Introduction

The aim of 6GTWINROAD-MNO is to design, evaluate, and test a context-aware AI-based architecture beyond 5G. This architecture will enable interaction between the network, its environment, and the Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) applications. It will allow the network to automatically change any parameter to provide seamless and safe experience for vehicle passengers.

In addition to the technical project activities, communication, dissemination, and standardization are essential for the success of the project. Therefore, this deliverable presents an intermediate report for dissemination, communication, and standardization in addition to the plan for future activities. This plan will be used as a guideline to successfully share project activities with targeted audiences, disseminate research outcomes, and create a momentum for standardization efforts together with the different stakeholders. It aims at maximising project visibility, impact, and contribution to the advancement of AI-enabled beyond 5G networks based on network digital twins and large-scale historical databases.

This deliverable provides thorough insights and valuable recommendations to the way project's activities are communicated, scientific results are disseminated, strategic collaborations with different stakeholders established, and novel outcomes are pushed to the standardisation bodies. Using the proposed work plan, the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project aims establishing strategic collaboration within the scientific community and industrial stakeholders to build a noticeable presence in these community and lead the efforts to have AI-Native 6G networks that can autonomously integrate new V2X services in an efficient way.

1.1 Document objectives

The Deliverable D5.1 aims at:

- Presenting the objectives, strategies, and activities towards effective dissemination of project's scientific results, communicating project's activities, creating strategic collaborations with stakeholders, and providing useful inputs to standardisation bodies.
- Explaining the current achievements of the project in terms of scientific dissemination, standardization, and communication activities and outlines the planned activities by highlighting the strategy to be implemented throughout project lifecycle. The strategy encompasses measurable impact indicators, such as the number of scientific publications, frequency of web posts, targeted standardisation forums, and a list of strategic events for project showcase.

1.2 Relation to the project's activities

This deliverable is framed within the Work Package 5 of the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project. This Work Package is responsible for promoting the dissemination of project results in scientific and industrial fora, engaging stakeholders, and research communities. It also emphasises the alignment with relevant standardisation activities and bodies, as well as open-source communities. Additionally, it focuses on exploiting project results by means of IPR generation, identification of licensing opportunities and creating synergistic collaborations among partners in Horizon Europe activities.

This deliverable is the joint result of tasks T5.1 and T5.2, which are outlined below:

T5.1 Communication, Outreach and Dissemination: This task ensures that the project outcomes are accessible to the broadest target audiences. Activities include, but are not limited to:

- Develop the project webpage and generate content in social media accounts.
- Create project flyers and brochures, to be always updated following the latest projects achievements.
- Monitor and engage with other research projects of the 5G/6G ecosystem.

T5.2 Exploitation and Internationalization: This task focuses on identifying exploitable results. To achieve this goal, the consistent and thorough management of innovation activities is a crucial foundation for creating and protecting IPRs, eventually realising concrete exploitation and business opportunities. This task also focuses on internationalizing the project results through other Horizon Europe initiatives.

Furthermore, this deliverable directly aligns with the core objectives of Work Package 5 of the 6GTWINROAD project. These objectives can be summarised as:

- Perform communication and outreach activities to guarantee that the project outcomes reach the public.
- Maximise the impact of the project through dissemination in scientific conferences and journals, as well as contributions to relevant standard bodies.
- Exploit project results by means of IPR generation, identification of licensing opportunities and creating synergistic collaborations among partners in Horizon Europe activities.

1.3 Deliverable overview

The remainder of this document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 provides an overview of the project's communication and outreach activities.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the project's dissemination activities.

- Section 4 provides an overview of the project's standardisation activities.
- Section 5 provides impact indicators.
- Section 6 concludes the document.

2 Communication and outreach activities

Communication and outreach activities aim to support and maximise 6GTWINROAD project impact. The specific objectives of these activities are:

- Raise awareness about the 6GTWINROAD project among relevant stakeholders and key audiences, including academia, industry, policymakers, and the general public.
- Engage with relevant stakeholder groups, tailoring the content to their specific needs and interests and establishing a distinctive identity to support promotional purposes.
- Effectively promote project's activities and achievements by using various communication tools and platforms, including websites, social media, and events.
- Facilitate information sharing, collaboration, and coordination among team members by establishing clear and consistent internal communication channels within the project consortium.

The first phase of the plan aimed to raising awareness about the project, identifying key stakeholder communities and target audiences. The progress will be communicated through various channels and activities until reaching a phase where the main aim is to promote results and uptake by external communities.

From a communication point of view, the focus is to ensure that relevant stakeholders such as research communities and organisations involved in activities and topics relevant to 6GTWINROAD-MNO are aware of the project's existence, motivation, expected outcomes, and how those results can benefit them according to their roles.

2.1 Communication plan

Communication activities are essential to build a strong impact strategy along with dissemination and standardization efforts. Considering the duration of the project, the planned technical progress and the main milestones, and the intertwining between communication, dissemination, and standardisation efforts, three phases are defined:

1. **Awareness creation:** This phase intends to design the communication strategy and plan, including identification of key stakeholder communities and target audiences with whom the project can begin to establish relationships. It also aims to identify relevant projects and initiatives, to find common practices, synergies, and opportunities for collaboration in community-building activities. From a communication point of view, the focus is on ensuring that people and organisations involved in activities and topics relevant for 6GTWINROAD-MNO are aware of the project's existence, motivation, expected outcomes, and how those results can benefit them according to their roles. Moreover, introducing the partners involved

in the project and the scenarios where the technologies developed will be validated constitutes another valuable topic to share with external audiences.

2. **Community outreach:** This phase is intended to demonstrate the progress and to engage with relevant stakeholders to collect valuable feedback considering their various points of view.
3. **Global outreach and sustainable impact:** This phase aims at actively engage and support the uptake and deployment of the concepts, technologies and tools offered by 6GTWINROAD-MNO through dedicated promotional activities and materials, publicity of validation activities, further scientific publications, participation in selected events, organisation of planned workshops and exploitation activities with the aim to demonstrate to potential adopters the relevance of the project's technologies and benefits.

2.2 Activities performed by i2CAT

The main communication activities performed by i2CAT involve the creation of project materials, and the establishment of communication channels and tools.

2.2.1 Project materials

The definition and generation of the brand and visual elements of 6GTWINROAD has a significant impact on the execution of various activities, as the goal is to share a consistent and coherent image of the project regardless of the activity, venue, partner participating, etc.

To create a visual identity for the project, report and presentation templates, and videos are used to enhance the dissemination efforts and effectively communicate the project's objectives, key findings, and achievements to different target audiences:

- **Report templates:** to establish a common visual model to deliver technical reports and deliverables about the project developments, highlighting main novelties in relation to the state-of-the-art.
- **Presentation templates:** to establish a common visual model to deliver engaging and informative presentations about the project overview, highlighting main novelties in relation to the state-of-the-art.
- **Videos:** for conveying information in an appealing and accessible manner. The project may utilise videos to showcase demonstrations, explain technical concepts, or present project highlights. Videos can be shared on the project website, social media platforms, or included in presentations and demos to captivate the audience and increase the visibility and understanding of the project's work.

This visual identity is applied consistently across all communication materials, including the deliverables, presentations, and promotional items. The visual identity not only creates a cohesive and appealing visual experience but also contributes to the overall

success of the project's communication and dissemination efforts. The following visual identity guidelines are followed in the project:

- All publications, communications, and websites associated with the project shall indicate the funding entities, namely the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union – NextGenerationEU. This acknowledgment will be in line with the "framework of the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience (PRTR)" as specified in article 34.2 of the "Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council".
- The visual identity of the project shall be maintained by displaying the UE banner with the statement "funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU" in all communication activities. Additionally, the logo of the PRTR will be incorporated appropriately. These elements shall be included in various communication materials, including posters, electronic publications, and the project website.
- The project is committed to promoting gender equality, inclusivity, and diversity in all communication activities. Images that discriminate against women will be avoided, and communication materials will aim to represent a diverse range of roles and perspectives. It is essential to refrain from using sexist language in all project-related communication activities.

By respecting the established visual identity guidelines, the 6GTWINROAD project ensures a consistent and coherent representation across all communication channels and materials. This approach not only highlights the project's funding sources but also promotes gender equality, diversity, and inclusivity throughout its communication activities.

2.2.1.1 Document Templates

In order to maintain a consistent and professional visual identity for the 6GTWIROAD-MNO project, a comprehensive set of document templates has been created. These templates serve as standardised formats for presentations, deliverables, and other project reports. The availability of these templates ensures that all project members and subcontractors can create materials that adhere to the established visual identity guidelines.

The document templates have been thoughtfully designed to showcase the project's key information and results in a visually appealing and cohesive manner. They incorporate the funding logos, project's identifier, and other relevant visual elements. By utilising these standardised templates, project members can easily create high-quality documents that maintain a consistent look and feel across all project deliverables. In this way, the 6GTWIROAD-MNO project can effectively communicate its progress, findings, and achievements in a visually appealing and coherent manner.

An example of the project's deliverable template can be seen in Figure 1. This template provides a structured layout with predefined sections for the document's objectives,

scope, structure, and conclusions. It also includes placeholders for tables, figures, and acronyms to effectively illustrate and support the presented information.

Figure 1: 6GTWIROAD-MNO deliverable template.

Another example is the project presentation template that can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2 6GTWIROAD-MNO presentation template.

Access to these document templates is granted to all project members and subcontractors, ensuring that everyone involved in the project can produce materials that align with the established visual identity.

2.2.2 Communication Tools

This section outlines the various tools and platforms that will be leveraged to reach the target audience through digital channels. By employing a diverse array of communication tools, the project aims to maximise its outreach, enhance knowledge sharing, and foster collaboration within the relevant communities.

2.2.2.1 Project Website

The project website plays a crucial role in facilitating dissemination and communication activities. With a focus on providing a seamless user experience, a common website for the UNICO I+D 6G program¹ coordinated by i2CAT has been developed to cater for both desktop and mobile users, following responsive design principles. Moreover, the website adheres to the Visual Identity requirements established by the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience from the Spanish Government². This space, depicted in Figure 3, provides key information about the program and summarises the different projects framed within this initiative. Visitors can access detailed information about the

¹ <https://i2cat.net/unico/>

² <https://planderecuperacion.gob.es/identidad-visual>

program’s activities and updates, both past and upcoming. Additionally, the site serves as a centralised repository for ongoing tendering calls.

On the aforementioned website, a dedicated subsite has been integrated specifically for the 6GTWINROAD coordinated project³. This subsite offers a comprehensive overview of the project, including its main objectives and a brief introduction to each one of the sub-projects, including 6GTWINROAD-MNO, as illustrated in Figure 4. Acting as a dedicated space for dissemination and communication, the website will provide access to a wide range of materials, including technical specifications, reports, blogs, videos, and news about events and activities such as conferences and exhibitions. It will serve as the primary source of information regarding the project's activities, developments, and results and will be the primary platform for sharing projects results and updates with the general audience.

Figure 3: Website for the UNICO I+D 6G program coordinated by i2CAT.

Figure 4: 6GTWINROAD subsite.

³ <https://i2cat.net/unico/6gtwinroad/>

To effectively disseminate the project's achievements, the 6GTWINROAD subsite includes a dedicated "News" section. This section will provide regular updates on the project's progress, milestones, and notable accomplishments. It serves as a valuable resource for visitors to stay informed about the latest developments and milestones.

Furthermore, the website incorporates a "Documents" section providing access to open-access scientific publications related to the project, including journals, conferences, workshops, and other relevant sources. To enhance the user experience and provide further relevant information, the subsite includes links to other relevant sites, such as blog posts from the project, fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration.

In order to ensure the long-term accessibility of project results, the UNICO I+D 6G program website, which hosts the 6GTWINROAD subsite, will remain active for a minimum of two years after the conclusion of the project. This guarantees the sustained availability of valuable project information and resources.

Overall, the 6GTWINROAD subsite serves as a comprehensive platform for disseminating project updates, sharing research findings, and providing access to valuable resources, fostering engagement and knowledge exchange with the project's target audience. It plays a crucial role in communication and dissemination efforts, ensuring effective engagement with the general audience and facilitating knowledge dissemination within the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project.

2.2.2.2 Social Media

The 6GTWINROAD project recognises the significance of social media platforms, which play a crucial role in facilitating communication, dissemination, and engagement with stakeholders. Therefore, the project actively maintains a presence on social media, leveraging these platforms to disseminate news, events, and achievements. Specifically, i2CAT's Twitter⁴ and LinkedIn⁵ accounts serve as key channels for sharing project updates and news, ensuring that the latest developments are communicated effectively to a wide audience. Leveraging these social media accounts, the project aims to reach a wide and diverse audience by conducting targeted campaigns centred around project news, events, and achievements.

The project acknowledges the unique audience offered by the Twitter platform, particularly when combined with the use of hashtags. Figure 5 provides an example of previous communication efforts carried out by i2CAT via its X (formerly Twitter) account.

⁴ <https://twitter.com/i2CAT>

⁵ <https://es.linkedin.com/company/i2cat-foundation>

Figure 5: 6GTWINROAD post on i2CAT's X account.

Similarly, the 6GTWINROAD project has extended its reach to the i2CAT LinkedIn account, recognising it as a preferred platform for researchers, companies, and industry professionals. LinkedIn plays a significant role in facilitating communication and sharing news, events, and outcomes related to the project. By utilising the project consortium's individual pages on LinkedIn, posts can be easily shared, amplifying the impact and reach of dissemination and communication activities. Figure 6 provides an example of previous communication efforts carried out by i2CAT via its LinkedIn account.

i2CAT
12,439 followers
5mo · 🌐

📶🚌 Investigadors del nostre centre assajaran a **#Terrassa** un sistema intel·ligent de regulació del trànsit per optimitzar el transport públic.

🚦👤 Aquest sistema es basarà en la creació d'un bessó digital vehicular que permetrà monitorar el trànsit i establir diferents nivells de prioritat per a la circulació dels vehicles a partir d'un pla de control intel·ligent dels semàfors.

🗣️ "L'objectiu és reduir la demora dels autobusos i limitar la intensitat de vehicles privats en la via", explica en **Francisco Vazquez Gallego**, líder de la línia de recerca en V2X a i2CAT.

🗣️ "Estem molt orgullosos que la nostra ciutat serveixi per assajar un sistema de regulació del trànsit que permetrà en un futur millorar l'eficiència del transport públic i donar un pas més cap a una mobilitat més respectuosa amb el medi ambient i més segura", assenyala **Xavier Cardona Ruiz**, tinent d'alcalde de Mobilitat a l'**Ajuntament de Terrassa**.

📦 Aquest cas d'ús, en el qual col·laboren les empreses **Aimsun** i **Acisa**, es durà a terme dins de **#6GTWINROAD**, un projecte de recerca inscrit en el programa **#UNICO** I+D 6G que finança el **Ministry of Economy, Trade and Business** i la Unió Europea a través dels fons del Pla de Recuperació, Transformació i Resiliència del Govern d'Espanya.

+ go.i2cat.net/dCI2zg

[See translation](#)

👤 Mària Sanchez Moreno and 29 others 1 comment · 2 reposts

Figure 6: 6GTWINROAD post on i2CAT's LinkedIn account.

By leveraging these platforms, the project can effectively share updates, highlight milestones, and engage with the public, industry professionals, and other relevant

communities. These examples serve as valuable references, demonstrating effective utilisation of social media platforms to disseminate project information, attract stakeholders, and foster collaboration.

To ensure comprehensive coverage, the i2CAT Corporate Development department works closely with the project's research team. This collaboration aims to keep track of the project's progress, identify significant achievements, and develop communication content that can attract media attention. Communication content is carefully crafted to highlight the project's innovations, advancements, and their potential impact on the field. i2CAT also integrates information about the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project into external campaigns that focus on disseminating the center's broader research strategy in the domains of 5G and 6G.

Through a combination of social media posts and news on the website, the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project aims to extend its reach beyond the project's immediate stakeholders. By effectively utilising social media platforms and engaging with the media, the project can maximise its visibility, create awareness about its objectives, and foster collaboration and knowledge exchange within the wider community.

2.2.2.3 Internal Communication

The internal communication plays a crucial role in facilitating effective collaboration, coordination, and knowledge sharing among the partners of the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project. A structured approach is followed to ensure effective communication and coordination among its participants. The various tools, platforms, and practices employed to foster seamless communication within the project team are outlined next.

Meetings: facilitate effective communication and collaboration among project partners, allowing team members to gather, discuss progress, exchange ideas, and address any challenges. Specifically, the project schedule includes a bi-weekly internal meetings covering both managerial and technical aspects, overseeing the project progress, and enabling decision making, commitments, and next steps. In addition, bi-weekly and ad-hoc meetings are held with the partners to discuss the progress of the different tasks and plan the next steps.

To facilitate seamless communication and collaboration, the project leverages dedicated platforms such as project management and collaboration systems for document sharing (i.e., google drive), virtual meetings software (i.e., Google Meet) and messaging tools (i.e., Gmail). These platforms enable team members to share project-related documentation, track progress, assign tasks, and collaborate on shared files in a centralised and organised manner. By utilising such platforms, the project team has real-time access to project-related information, enabling collaborative work in an efficient manner. In summary, the platforms employed to streamline internal communication and document sharing among the team involved in 6GTWINROAD-MNO include google drive, Google Meet, and Gmail.

Documentation plays a critical role in the internal communication by providing a comprehensive, updated and easily accessible repository of project-related information. Documentation includes technical documents, progress reports, meeting slides, and so forth. The project team has access to these documents to ensure transparency, facilitate knowledge transfer, and ensure consistency in the understanding project objectives and requirements. In order to enforce a consistent format, document templates are used for the delivery of project documentation (as presented in Section 2.2.1.1).

By implementing robust internal communication guidelines, the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project aims to foster a collaborative and cohesive environment where team members can effectively communicate, share knowledge, and work towards achieving project objectives. Established mechanisms and practices underscore the project's commitment to seamless internal communication, ensuring all team members are aligned, informed, and actively engaged in the project's progress.

2.2.3 Initial Outputs

Relevant communication actions performed include:

- Three internal UNICO I+D workshops held at i2CAT in December 2022, June 2023, and January 2024 respectively, which served as a platform to discuss project development strategy.
- A 6GTWINROAD-MNO and 6GTWINROAD-2 6G Vehicular Enablers for Road Operators workshop held at i2CAT on the 25th of May 2023. This served as an encounter point for project partners to discuss in person the technical details of the project's use cases and the integration plan in scope of the technologies developed in the project.
- i2CAT's UNICO I+D strategy presentation at the V5gValencia in November 2023, with a specific mention to the 6GTWINROAD project.

3 Dissemination activities

To maximize 6GTWINROAD-MNO project impact, the project also focused on dissemination activities such as scientific paper publication in journal and conferences. The specific objectives of the dissemination activities are:

- Make project's findings, insights, and outcomes available to the public to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native and context-aware Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN).
- Reach, stimulate, and engage various stakeholders from the various target areas to ensure that the results of 6GTWINROAD-MNO are effectively showcased. This can lead to validation, improvement and possibly wider adoption of the technologies and concepts developed.
- Maximise the visibility and impact of the project by effectively disseminating research findings, technical advancements, and innovative solutions through various channels and platforms.
- Engage and collaborate with relevant research, innovation and policy making initiatives, liaising with related projects, and working groups within 3GPP, IEEE, O-RAN, ETSI, or other relevant bodies.

The first phase of the dissemination plan was devoted to raising awareness about the project, identifying key stakeholder communities and target audiences. Then, for the second phase, the availability of partial results is fundamental to demonstrate the progress and engage with stakeholders targeted in the first phase, thus supporting business cases and exploitation tasks promoting the final results.

3.1 Activities performed by i2cat

To guarantee the accuracy and integrity of the research outcomes and enhance their impact and outreach, a standard publication procedure has been proposed. In addition, ongoing work is trying to identify projects to establish potential collaborations with.

3.1.1 Publication procedure and acknowledgements

The publication procedure aims at establishing clear guidelines for publications, including the review process, authorship, and acknowledgements, while ensuring proper recognition of funding sources, project partners, and contributors in all publications.

Within this procedure, the main author is responsible for circulating the final draft of the publication to the co-authors for review. This step ensures that all co-authors have an opportunity to provide input, suggest revisions, and verify the accuracy of the content. The feedback received from the co-authors will be incorporated into the final

version of the manuscript. The authors will be established according to the contribution to the paper writing and the technical/scientific work behind.

Furthermore, cross-organisation authorship will be fostered where possible to maximise the impact of the publication including multiple business corners and technical perspectives.

Once the final draft has been approved by all co-authors, the manuscript will be submitted to appropriate venues for further evaluation through the peer-review process. This process involves subjecting the publication to the scrutiny of independent experts in the relevant field who assess the scientific rigor, validity, and novelty of the research. Upon acceptance of the publication, it will be made available on the project's website, ensuring open access for interested parties. By sharing the publications on the website, the project aims to disseminate the knowledge and findings to a wide audience, including researchers and industry professionals.

As part of the publication procedure, it is crucial to acknowledge the contributions and support received throughout the project. Therefore, all publications, conference proceedings, presentations at workshops, seminars, or public events related to the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project must include the following acknowledgment text. This acknowledgment ensures proper recognition and attribution to the funding entities and stakeholders involved in the project:

“This project was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union – NextGeneration EU, in the framework of the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience (Call UNICO I+D 5G 2021, ref. number TSI-063000-2021-29).”

By adhering to a systematic publication procedure and acknowledging the project's funding sources, the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project ensures the quality, transparency, and accountability of its research publications.

3.1.2 Collaborations with other Projects

i2CAT is strongly involved in the European research ecosystem, participating in various Spanish, European H2020, and SNS projects. By joining forces with these projects, the conducted work and its dissemination will be strengthened, and its significance will be amplified. The following Spanish and EU projects have been identified as potential candidate for collaboration:

Open, Virtualized Technology Demonstrators for Smart Networks (Open-VERSO)

Open-VERSO is a Spanish project joining the efforts of three research centres (Vicomtech, Gradiant and i2CAT) to build an open, virtualised technology demonstrator for smart networks. The demonstrator is employed to accelerate the evolution of 5G and beyond networks. In this project, i2CAT has been focusing on the development, integration, and deployment of the following technologies: virtualized RAN controller; orchestration, monitoring and automation system for network resources and services; evolution of the 5G core network and the adaptation of a prototype of Microcontroller Unit (MCU) for volumetric video to the virtualized environment offered by Open-VERSO.

Trial Platform for 5G Evolution – Cross-Industry On Large Scale (TARGET-X)

TARGET-X is a Horizon JU SNS project with a total public private investment of almost €8 million in addition to €8 million that will be used for funding projects through open calls. The project was launched on the 1st of January 2023 and aims at accelerating the digital transformation of key verticals: energy, construction, automotive, and manufacturing using large-scale trials in multiple testbeds. In TARGET-X, i2CAT is leading WP4 that focuses on the automotive vertical. In this workpackage cooperative perception, digital twin, and predictive Quality of Service (QoS) tele-operated driving use cases will be developed and evaluated. In the latter an exposure Application Programming Interface (API) will be developed.

3.1.3 Initial Outputs

As a research institution, i2CAT aims to disseminate 6GTWINROAD-MNO results in high impact journal and magazine publications, as well as in high-calibre international conferences. Currently, the following conference paper was published:

- M. Trullenque Ortiz, O. Sallent, D. Camps-Mur, J. Escrig, J. Nasreddine, J. Pérez-Romero, "On the Application of Q-learning for Mobility Load Balancing in Realistic Vehicular Scenarios," IEEE 97th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC'23-Spring), Florence, Italy, June 2023

In addition, we are working on the following papers to be submitted in 2024:

- One magazine article about *O-RAN -based Architecture driven by Historical Information to Mitigate cell overloads for vehicular services over public 5G networks* to be tentatively submitted to IEEE communication magazine.
- One conference paper analysing the network KPI dataset obtained in WP3.

4 Standardization activities

Standardisation activities are intended to support and maximise the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project impact, by raising awareness and ensuring maximum visibility of project results and progress among stakeholders and key audiences. Standardization tactics are oriented toward ensuring that the project's outcomes align with existing standards and frameworks and, in turn, enhancing visibility of the EU funding. The concrete objectives of the standardisation plan are as follows:

- To identify relevant standardisation activities and initiatives in the field of industrial edge orchestration and industrial private-public integration models, ensuring the project's alignment with existing standards and frameworks.
- To incorporate standardisation requirements and considerations into the project's research, development, and deployment processes, promoting interoperability, compatibility, and scalability of the developed solutions.
- To contribute to the dissemination of standardisation outputs and promote their adoption within the wider Smart Industry and 5G/6G communities, fostering harmonisation and collaboration across different projects and initiatives.
- To identify opportunities and potentially participate in standardisation organisations, forums, and working groups to share project findings, insights, and recommendations, influencing the development of standards in the field.

4.1 Activities performed by i2cat

Although i2CAT has not performed any standardisation activities in the scope of the technical developments of the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project, it has however identified the following forums and standardisation bodies of interest to 6GTWINROAD-MNO, which it actively follows:

- O-RAN: i2CAT tracks progress in the O-RAN specification, due to its impact on the 6G future. Thus, the use of open interfaces, virtualization, software, and intelligent controllers to create automatic control loops is of interest for 6GTWINROAD activities.
- ETSI: i2CAT follows the work ETSI Software Development Groups (SDGs) that focuses on open-source initiatives, especially those related to network APIs and vertical integration such as OpenCAPIF
- 3GPP: i2CAT follows the standardization activities related to the different 5G RAN and Core releases, related to the provision of URLLC extreme KPIs.
- CAMARA project: i2CAT actively follows the CAMARA project developments to align the design of the network exposure API with the CAMARA framework to be able to take advantage of relevant APIs.

5 Impact management and indicators

This section describes the key impact indicators that are being monitored during the project's lifecycle, together with the impact management mechanisms used by i2CAT to monitor and manage relevant data. By using these two mechanisms, i2cat can ensure the deployment of effective monitoring and communication activities related to the 6GTWINROAD project and its different subprojects, specifically 6GTWINROAD-MNO.

5.1 Impact management

The 6GTWINROAD project (including 6GTWINROAD-MNO) has implemented publication and event tracking methodology that provides effective monitoring and planning of dissemination and communication activities. The implemented methodology increases the efficiency of the supervision task of the PI and Co-PI by enabling project's members to report dissemination and communication efforts in an easy way. The publication and event tracking methodology includes the following key elements:

1. **Reporting:** Project participants can use the regular and ad-hoc meetings to provide up-to-date reports including planned dissemination opportunities, event attendance, and publications related to the project. These reports serve as an updated overview of the ongoing and upcoming activities.
2. **Event information:** It includes essential details about events, such as the location, participants, contributions made by the project team, and any other relevant information. This allows the project to track its presence and contributions in different events accurately.
3. **Audience analysis:** Project partners are requested to provide information on the number and type of audience reached during events or dissemination activities. This helps in assessing the outreach and impact of the project's communication efforts and enables targeted engagement with specific stakeholder groups.
4. **Future outcomes and impact:** The reports also capture the projected outcomes and potential impact resulting from the conducted activities. This includes identifying potential publications, establishing new contacts, and other relevant future outcomes. By tracking these aspects, the project can evaluate the effectiveness and long-term impact of its dissemination and communication initiatives.

By implementing this event and publication tracking methodology, the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project gains valuable insights into its dissemination and communication efforts. The impact tracking report enables project members to assess the effectiveness of their activities, identify potential areas for improvement, and plan future actions. Furthermore, the integration of these reports into the project's deliverables provides a comprehensive record of the project's dissemination and communication achievements over time. This tracking methodology enhances the project's ability to measure its

impact, facilitate collaboration, and ensure the successful delivery of its dissemination and communication objectives.

5.2 Impact Indicators

To assess the performance and effectiveness of the dissemination and communication activities of the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project, a set of impact indicators has been established. These Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will provide valuable insights into the reach, engagement, and influence of the project's dissemination and communication efforts to ensure the project's objectives are effectively communicated to target audiences maximising its impact. Table 1 lists the KPIs defined to measure the impact generation of 6GTWINROAD-MNO project.

Table 1 6GTWINROAD-MNO impact indicators.

Type	KPI	Target
Website	Blog and news entries	At least one blogpost per partner organisation
LinkedIn	Posts mentioning #6GTWINROAD, #UNICO6G and/or #UNICO	1 post per month
X	Posts mentioning #6GTWINROAD, #UNICO6G or #UNICO	1 post per month
Marketing material	Slide presentations	1 slide deck for the project overview
	Brochures	1 set (to cover i2CAT's UNICO programme)
	Videos	1
	Publications in partners' newsletters	2
Scientific dissemination	Scientific publications in conferences	Acknowledgement in 2 conference papers
	Articles in specialised magazines and/or journals	Acknowledgement in 1 journal or magazine article
Standardisation and pre-standardisation	Number of standards monitored	4
Events	Workshops organised	1 for the 6GTWIROAD
	Attendees to project workshops	20 for the 6GTWINROAD
	Demo events/videos	3 demo videos for the 6GTWINROAD coordinated project

Collaboration	Liaisons and joint activities with other projects, communities, initiatives, etc. (e.g., website links, workshops, newsletters, social media, joint publications, etc.)	3
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6 Conclusions

In this deliverable, the results of the communication, dissemination, and standardization plan and activities during the first period of the project have been presented. Impact indicators have also been defined, common to the other UNICO projects. During the second period, the objective is to increase the communication and dissemination of the project, since there will be results of the technical tasks and the evaluations of the technologies proposed in 6GTWINROAD-MNO under the framework of the demonstrators. It is also intended to increase cooperation with the other project partners in this area, with a focus on scientific and industrial dissemination.